

**New and rare fungus weevil and snout beetle species in Hungary
(Coleoptera: Curculionoidea)**

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Abstract – *Eusphyrus vasconicus* (A. Hoffmann et Tempère, 1954), a fungus weevil species (Coleoptera: Anthribidae), is reported from Hungary for the first time. Recent records of *Mogulones albolineatus* (J. Frivaldszky, 1878), *Otiorhynchus aurifer* Boheman, 1842, *Ranunculiphilus italicus* (C. N. F. Brisout de Barneville, 1869), *Rhinusa rara* Toševski et Caldara, 2015, and *Stenocarus ruficornis* (Stephens, 1831) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) are also presented.

Key words – Palearctic Region, faunistics, new country record

INTRODUCTION

The author and his friends are involved in various conservation projects, which provides the possibility to collect and study the weevil fauna (Coleoptera: Curculionoidea) of different areas in Hungary. The present paper publishes locality data of some rare species of true weevils (Curculionidae); additionally, a fungus weevil species (Coleoptera: Anthribidae), collected during a field trip organised by the WWF Hungary and the Hungarian Biodiversity Research Society in Örtilos (Somogy County) in 2025, is reported for the first time from Hungary. The here published new country record raises the species number of Curculionoidea known from Hungary to 1236 (SZÉNÁSI 2025, TRNKA *et al.* 2025). All specimens were identified by the author.

Abbreviations – CAM = private collection of András Márkus (Gyula, Hungary), CVS = private collection of Valentin Szénási (Isaszeg, Hungary), HNHM = Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary).

SPECIES NEW TO HUNGARY

Anthribidae

Eusphyrus vasconicus (A. Hoffmann et Tempère, 1954)
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – **Somogy County:** Őrtilos, Dráva-floodplain, 27.VI.2025, leg. M. Lukátsi (3 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species has been known from France, Italy, and Spain (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). Since all congeners of *Eusphyrus vasconicus* occur in America, its European records (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2008, CORNACCHIA & COLONNELLI 2012, FREEMAN & VALLET 2003, present study) raise the question whether this species is native or introduced to Europe. Proposed Hungarian name: “fűzfa-orrosbogár”.

NEW RECORDS OF RARE OR NOTEWORTHY SPECIES

Curculionidae

Mogulones albolineatus (J. Frivaldszky, 1878)
(Fig. 2)

Material examined – **Bács-Kiskun County:** Lajosmizse, Fecske-erdő, from *Onosma arenaria* Waldst. et Kit. (Boraginaceae), 13.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM). **Csongrád County:** Ásotthalom, Emlékerdő, from *Onosma arenaria*, 7.VII.2025, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS). **Pest County:** Nagykáta, Cseh-domb, from *Onosma arenaria*, 10.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); Nagykáta, Erdőszőlőilegelő, from *Onosma arenaria*, 1.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Nagykáta, Szőlőalja-dűlő, from *Onosma arenaria*, 10.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Nagykáta, Új-hegy, from *Onosma arenaria*, 17.X.2025, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Nagykörös, near Makkos-tanya, from *Onosma arenaria*, 13.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Nagykörös, Strázsa-hegy, from *Onosma arenaria*, 13.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); Szentmártonkáta, Gicei-hegy, from *Onosma arenaria*, 22.X.2025, 1.XII.2025, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS); Szentmártonkáta, shooting area, from *Onosma arenaria*, 23.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM).

Remarks – Occurrence data are increasing as a result of targeted research; however, the species is virtually absent from a significant proportion of suitable habitats. Still a very rare, endangered species in Hungary.

Otiorhynchus aurifer Boheman, 1842

Material examined – **Budapest:** District V, József nádor square, 8.X.2025, leg. M. Lukátsi, V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM).

Remarks – Second record from Hungary. This species occurs mainly in Southern Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023); however, in the recent years it has been expanding, mainly in human environments (SZÉNÁSI 2025).

Rhinusa rara Tošovski et Caldara, 2015
(Fig. 3)

Material examined – **Pest County:** Isaszeg, Dump, from *Linaria genistifolia* (L.) Mill. (Plantaginaceae), 23.VII.2025, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS); Szada, Ivacsok, from *Linaria genistifolia*, 21.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); Sződ, Debegió-hegy, from *Linaria genistifolia*, 20.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens in CVS); Tura, sand mine, from *Linaria genistifolia*, 21.VI.2025, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS).

Remarks – This species, distributed in Europe, is considered as rare (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). Targeted research reveals that, at least within Hungary, it is far from rare.

Ranunculiphilus italicus (C. N. F. Brisout de Barneille, 1869)

Material examined – **Baranya County:** Nagyharsány, Szársomlyó-hill, 29.V.2023, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS). **Békés County:** Gyula, Bánomdűlő, 27.V.2025, leg. A. Márkus (2 specimens in CAM).

Remarks – This Palearctic species is considered rare (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). It is similarly scarce in Hungary, with only very limited data available.

Stenocarus ruficornis (Stephens, 1831)
(Fig. 4)

Material examined – **Békés County:** Gyula, Gárdonyi street, from wall of house, 8.VII.2022, leg. A. Márkus (1 specimens in CAM).

Remarks – This very common Palearctic species (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023) was only included in this paper due to the atypical pattern of colouration of the specimen reported here (Fig. 4).

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2

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Figs 1–4. Habitus photos of the voucher specimens, 1 = *Eusphyrus vasconicus* (A. Hoffmann et Tempère, 1954), 2 = *Mogulones albolineatus* (J. Frivaldszky, 1878), 3 = *Rhinusa rara* Tošovskí et Caldara, 2015, 4 = *Stenocarus ruficornis* (Stephens, 1831). Not to scale (photos by Valentin Szénási)

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Acknowledgements – Thanks are due to the WWF Hungary and the Hungarian Biodiversity Research Society for organising the field trip where the voucher specimens of *Eusphyrus vasconicus* were collected. I would like to thank everyone who contributed to this study, chiefly Győző Szél and Aranka Grabant (HNHM) for the possibility to review relevant parts of the collection under their care. Thanks are also due to Márk Lukátsi and András Márkus for collecting weevils (either with me or for me), and to Tamás Németh for post-processing the figures.

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